

Use of internet-based mobile phone app messaging services by health workers and managers in LMICs: rapid scoping review of qualitative studies

Protocol – version 11/01/2021

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Background

- Digital strategies for healthcare services and health systems are being developed and rolled out globally by health service organisations. Many of these strategies and programmes include components that enable digital communication between health workers and patients and between health workers and their colleagues/peers, managers and other parts of the health system. Recent studies and reviews have documented a number of challenges in implementing these strategies and programmes, particularly in LICs (1)
- In addition, health workers and managers are using the publicly available internet-based mobile phone app and in-app messaging services available to them to increase communication. For instance, health workers and managers are using internet-based mobile phone app messaging services like Telegram and WhatsApp to address different challenges in their frontline work, for example to communicate with colleagues in referral hospitals or to check the availability of commodities in neighbouring health facilities
- While some qualitative studies have explored this use of internet-based messaging services, these studies have not been collated or reviewed. This scoping review will provide a summary of the key characteristics of all qualitative studies conducted to date of the use of internet-based mobile phone app messaging services by health workers and managers in LMICs in LMICs, and of how these messaging services are being used by healthcare workers and managers

Aim of the scoping review

To systematically identify and map qualitative research on the use of internet-based mobile phone apps (technically also referred to as Voice over Internet Protocol (VoIP)) and in-app messaging services for person-to-person interactions by health workers and managers in low- and middle-income countries.

We will use the results of this scoping review to identify research gaps and plan a research agenda, including the feasibility of a QES on this topic.

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of studies

- We will include primary studies that use qualitative study designs such as ethnography, phenomenology, case studies, grounded theory studies and qualitative process evaluations. We will include studies that use both qualitative methods for data collection (e.g. focus group discussions, individual interviews, observation, diaries, document analysis, open-ended survey questions) *and* qualitative methods for data analysis (e.g. thematic analysis, framework analysis, grounded theory).
- We will exclude studies that collect data using qualitative methods but do not analyze these data using qualitative analysis methods (e.g. open-ended survey questions where the response data are analyzed using descriptive statistics only).
- We will include both published and unpublished studies in English, Portuguese, Spanish and the Scandinavian languages. We will exclude studies published in other languages due to the very short timeline for this review. However, studies in other languages that have an abstract in one of the included languages and appear eligible will be flagged for future follow up.
- We will include studies regardless of when they were undertaken or published.
- We will include mixed-methods studies where it is possible to extract information on the data that were collected and analyzed using qualitative methods.
- We will include protocols for studies that meet our other eligibility criteria.

Topic of interest

We will include studies of healthcare workers' and managers' perceptions and experiences of using internet-based mobile phone app and in-app messaging services such as Telegram, Signal, Whatsapp and Facebook groups for person-to-person interactions or communication in their work. This includes:

- Healthcare worker and manager levels: communication between healthcare workers, including seeking information, clinical guidance and support (including telemedicine); communication between managers (one-to-one and in peer or other groups), including seeking information and support; communication between healthcare workers and their supervisors / managers, including where healthcare workers are seeking information, clinical guidance or support (including telemedicine); transmission of information to healthcare workers; coordinating emergency responses and transport; managing referrals; scheduling activities; providing training content to healthcare workers; prescription and medication management; sending or receiving diagnostic orders and results and tracking specimens; human resource and supply chain management; public health event notification; and managing facilities
- Client level: healthcare workers or health services using messaging services to transmit targeted information, health event alerts, diagnostic results or reminders to clients

We will include person-to-person interactions or communication via any channel including messaging, voice notes, media exchange (such as images), data exchange or a combination of channels.

Relevant internet-based messaging services include:

- Publicly available internet-based mobile phone app and in-app messaging services such as Bridgefy, Chatbot, Facebook Messenger and Facebook groups, Instagram, Kakao, Keybase, Kik, Line, MessengerPeople, Signal, Siilo, Skype, Slack, Snapchat, Telegram, Threema, Tiger, Trillian, Twitter, Viber, Vibes, WeChat, Whatsapp and Wire
- Internet-based mobile phone app and in-app messaging services designed specifically for health services, and which also include messaging functions. These platforms include Hospify, Medic Bleep, SimplePractice, OnCall Health and Weltell. In-app messaging services linked to internet-based learning platforms, such as Moodle and Edmodo LMS, provided these meet the other inclusion criteria for this review.

We will exclude studies that focus on the following:

- Healthcare workers', managers' and clients' use of SMS or mobile phone calls as these platforms has different functionalities and costs and have been assessed in other reviews
- Healthcare workers' and managers' use of apps only to: (a) collect data (such as patient data) during one-to-one interactions with clients; (b) collect and / or use routine health service data; and (c) collect data for research purposes (such as conducting research interviews via mobile phone apps), as these kinds of activity are not primarily about communicating with clients
- The use of these messaging services for advertising a commercial health service. For example, to advertise fertility or dental services
- Internet-based messaging services that are designed to only provide clinical decision support to healthcare providers and do not involve communication between people
- The use of these messaging services among *pre-licensure* healthcare students (including for selecting or training students) unless they are working with post-licensure healthcare workers as part of a team, and are providing healthcare as part of their clinical practice training. However, we will include studies of in-service training
- Developing relevant mobile phone apps and in-app messaging services but with little or no data on the use of these apps
- Possible future use of digital interventions for health in general

We will include studies that consider both relevant internet-based messaging services and SMS, if it is possible to extract separately data on the relevant internet-based messaging services.

Types of participants

- Any health worker (including professional and lay (community) health workers) in LMICs using internet-based messaging services as described above
- Health service managers in LMICs using internet-based messaging services as described above

We will exclude studies focusing only on client use, or client-to-client use, of internet-based messaging services for health purposes. However, we will include studies involving bi-directional communication between health workers and clients.

Types of settings

We will include studies that collected data in any country classified by the World Bank at any time as an LMIC (see Medline search strategy below for a list of these countries (line 53)). We will include studies undertaken in multiple countries, provided that it is possible to extract the data from the LMICs specifically.

We will include studies conducted in any healthcare setting in an LMIC, including community-based care, primary health facilities and any other level of care; in outpatient and inpatient facilities; and in healthcare management and administration departments.

Search methods for identification of studies

An Information Specialist will develop the search strategies in consultation with the review authors.

We will search the following electronic databases:

- MEDLINE, Ovid
- Scopus, Elsevier.

We will develop search strategies for each database. We will not apply any limits on language or publication date. We will search all databases from inception to the date of search. See [Appendix 1](#) for final search strategies.

We will also request published and unpublished papers and reports from the [Global Digital Health Network](#) – a “networking forum with members from 117 countries to share information, engage with the broader community, and provide leadership in digital health for global public health”.

Selection of studies

Two review authors will independently assess each title and abstract of the identified records to evaluate eligibility. We will retrieve the full text of all the papers identified as potentially relevant by either or both review authors. Two review authors will then assess these papers independently. We will resolve disagreements by discussion or, when required, by involving a third review author.

We will include a PRISMA flow diagram to show our search results and the process of screening and selecting studies for **inclusion**. Where the same study (i.e. using the same sample and methods) has been presented in different reports, we will collate these reports so that each study (rather than each report) is the unit of interest in our review. We will include a table listing the references of studies that we excluded from our review at full-text stage, and the main reason/s for exclusion.

Extraction of study information and charting

We will develop and pilot a data extraction form. One review author will extract and chart study characteristics and data into the categories of the data extraction form. One review author will check all extracted data. Where data is not available in relation to a category, we will indicate this as 'not reported'. These categories will include the following:

- Study information:
 - Lead author
 - Year of publication
- Aim/s or objective/s of the study
- Study participants and settings:
 - Country/ies in which the research was undertaken
 - WHO region in which the research was undertaken (AFRO, EMRO, EURO, PAHO, SEARO, WPRO), [based on the current WHO classification](#)
 - Types of participants using the online messaging service (healthcare workers (lay health workers, nurses, midwives, doctors, pharmacists etc.), managers, clients etc.)
 - Healthcare setting/s in which the online messaging service is being used (community-based, primary care, secondary care, across primary and secondary etc.)
- Methods:
 - Type of qualitative data collection (individual interviews, focus group discussions, document analysis, observation, other – specify, unclear)
 - Type of qualitative data analysis (thematic, framework, etc., unclear) [extract term/s used in the paper]
- Online messaging service:
 - Name of messaging service (Signal, Telegram, etc.)
 - Problem / health service challenge or gap addressed by the messaging service (e.g., lack of or inappropriate referrals, insufficient supply of commodities) classified as far as possible using the [WHO classification](#) ((2) page 4) of health systems challenges in relation to digital health interventions
 - Purpose of use (classified as far as possible using the [WHO classification](#) ((2) pages 6-9) of digital health interventions, including by whether intended primarily for healthcare workers, health systems managers or clients)
 - Type of communication channel, e.g., messaging, voice notes, media exchange (such as images) or data exchange
 - How long the messaging service has been used (in years) in the context of the specific use/s described in the study
 - Number of individuals and / or groups involved in the messaging service
 - Who initiated the platform/s (healthcare providers in the public sector, healthcare managers in the public sector, healthcare providers in the private sector, healthcare managers in the private sector, NGO, bilateral aid agency, multilateral aid agency, other (specify))
 - Who provides technical support to users for their use of the service (healthcare providers in the public sector, healthcare managers in the public sector, healthcare providers in the private sector, healthcare managers in the private sector, NGO, bilateral aid agency, multilateral aid agency, other (specify), no support provided)
 - Use of the service for COVID-19 related activities (Yes / No – if yes, describe how the service was used)
- Study findings regarding healthcare workers', managers and other stakeholders' view of the use of online messaging services: we will tag full text papers that include thick descriptions of findings that relate closely to the review aim but no analysis of these data will be undertaken.

We will not assess the methodological limitations of the included studies as these data are not required for this scoping review.

Collation, summary and reporting of the results

We will **collate**, summarize and report the extracted data, using the categories outlined. This will include collating the number of studies and the types of messaging service used by the following:

- country
- WHO region
- Types of healthcare worker
- Types of setting.

Figures and tables will be used as needed.

References

1. Odendaal WA, Anstey Watkins J, Leon N, Goudge J, Griffiths F, Tomlinson M, et al. Health workers' perceptions and experiences of using mHealth technologies to deliver primary healthcare services: a qualitative evidence synthesis. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2020;3:CD011942.
2. WHO. Classification of digital health interventions v1. 0: a shared language to describe the uses of digital technology for health. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2018.

Contributions of authors

CG, SL and SMB devised this review. SL led the protocol preparation process with input and revisions from all members of the team. SL is the guarantor of this review.

Sources of support

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Declarations of interest

CF, CG, DM, MB, SL, SMB and TT declare no known financial conflicts of interest.

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Appendix 1: Search strategies

MEDLINE, Ovid

#	Searches	Results
1	Mobile Applications/	6672
2	Smartphone/	5030
3	Cell Phone/	8740
4	Text Messaging/	3143
5	or/1-4 [relevant MeSH]	19985
6	WhatsApp.ti,ab,kf.	604
7	Telegram.ti,ab,kf.	62
8	Facebook Messenger.ti,ab,kf.	17
9	Signal Private Messenger.ti,ab,kf.	0
10	Signal app.ti,ab,kf.	1
11	Bridgefy.ti,ab,kf.	0
12	Kik.ti,ab,kf.	57
13	Snapchat.ti,ab,kf.	101
14	Skype.ti,ab,kf.	412
15	Keybase.ti,ab,kf.	0
16	Viber.ti,ab,kf.	16
17	Vibes.ti,ab,kf.	42
18	Threema.ti,ab,kf.	0
19	Siilo.ti,ab,kf.	1
20	Hospify.ti,ab,kf.	1
21	SimplePractice.ti,ab,kf.	0
22	Oncall health.ti,ab,kf.	0
23	Trillian.ti,ab,kf.	0
24	Medic Bleep.ti,ab,kf.	3
25	WeChat.ti,ab,kf.	381
26	MessengerPeople.ti,ab,kf.	2
27	Snapchat.ti,ab,kf.	101
28	Instagram.ti,ab,kf.	660
29	Twitter.ti,ab,kf.	3630
30	Chatbot.ti,ab,kf.	145
31	Kakao.ti,ab,kf.	6
32	(Line and (app or apps or application? or platform)).ti,ab,kf.	38296
33	Wire.ti,ab,kf.	36047

34	Tiger.ti,ab,kf.	4261
35	Slack.ti,ab,kf.	1433
36	or/6-35 [WhatsApp and alternative tools]	85557
37	((mobile health or mhealth or m-health or chat or chatting or messaging) adj (app or apps or application? or platform? or system? or service? or technolog* or tool?)).ti,ab,kf.	3544
38	(informal adj (mobile health or mhealth or m-health)).ti,ab,kf.	5
39	((cellphone or cell* phone or mobile or smartphone or smart phone) adj (app or apps or application? or messaging or messages)).ti,ab,kf.	8842
40	((mobile phone or mobile telephone) adj (app or apps or application?)).ti,ab,kf.	856
41	(text messaging or texting or text messages).ti,ab,kf.	4378
42	((mobile or instans) adj messaging).ti,ab,kf.	63
43	((short messag* or multimedia messag*) adj service?).ti,ab,kf.	1304
44	((sms or mms or communication) adj (app or apps or application?)).ti,ab,kf.	317
45	messaging software.ti,ab,kf.	17
46	or/37-45 [general terms for communication tools]	16418
47	5 or 36 or 46	114074
48	Qualitative Research/	58849
49	Interviews as Topic/	63764
50	(qualitative or interview* or themes or mixed method?).ti,ab,kf.	563505
51	48 or 49 or 50	582827
52	47 and 51	5397
53	(afghanistan or albania or algeria or american samoa or angola or "antigua and barbuda" or antigua or barbuda or argentina or armenia or armenian or aruba or azerbaijan or bahrain or bangladesh or barbados or republic of belarus or belarus or byelarus or belorussia or byelorussian or belize or british honduras or benin or dahomey or bhutan or bolivia or "bosnia and herzegovina" or bosnia or herzegovina or botswana or bechuanaland or brazil or brasil or bulgaria or burkina faso or burkina fasso or upper volta or burundi or urundi or cabo verde or cape verde or cambodia or kampuchea or khmer republic or cameroon or cameron or cameroun or central african republic or ubangi shari or chad or chile or china or colombia or comoros or comoro islands or iles comores or mayotte or democratic republic of the congo or democratic republic congo or congo or zaire or costa rica or "cote d'ivoire" or "cote d'ivoire" or cote divoire or cote d ivoire or ivory coast or croatia or cuba or cyprus or czech republic or czechoslovakia or djibouti or french somaliland or dominica or dominican republic or ecuador or egypt or united arab republic or el salvador or equatorial guinea or spanish guinea or eritrea or estonia or eswatini or swaziland or ethiopia or fiji or gabon or gabonese	1986255

<p>republic or gambia or "georgia (republic)" or georgian or ghana or gold coast or gibraltar or greece or grenada or guam or guatemala or guinea or guinea bissau or guyana or british guiana or haiti or hispaniola or honduras or hungary or india or indonesia or timor or iran or iraq or isle of man or jamaica or jordan or kazakhstan or kazakh or kenya or "democratic people's republic of korea" or republic of korea or north korea or south korea or korea or kosovo or kyrgyzstan or kirghizia or kirgizstan or kyrgyz republic or kirghiz or laos or lao pdr or "lao people's democratic republic" or latvia or lebanon or lebanese republic or lesotho or basutoland or liberia or libya or libyan arab jamahiriya or lithuania or macau or macao or republic of north macedonia or macedonia or madagascar or malagasy republic or malawi or nyasaland or malaysia or malay federation or malaya federation or maldives or indian ocean islands or indian ocean or mali or malta or micronesia or federated states of micronesia or kiribati or marshall islands or nauru or northern mariana islands or palau or tuvalu or mauritania or mauritius or mexico or moldova or moldovian or mongolia or montenegro or morocco or ifni or mozambique or portuguese east africa or myanmar or burma or namibia or nepal or netherlands antilles or nicaragua or niger or nigeria or oman or muscat or pakistan or panama or papua new guinea or new guinea or paraguay or peru or philippines or philipines or phillipines or phillippines or poland or "polish people's republic" or portugal or portuguese republic or puerto rico or romania or russia or russian federation or ussr or soviet union or union of soviet socialist republics or rwnda or ruanda or samoa or pacific islands or polynesia or samoan islands or navigator island or navigator islands or "sao tome and principe" or saudi arabia or senegal or serbia or seychelles or sierra leone or slovakia or slovak republic or slovenia or melanesia or solomon island or solomon islands or norfolk island or norfolk islands or somalia or south africa or south sudan or sri lanka or ceylon or "saint kitts and nevis" or "st. kitts and nevis" or saint lucia or "st. lucia" or "saint vincent and the grenadines" or saint vincent or "st. vincent" or grenadines or sudan or suriname or surinam or dutch guiana or netherlands guiana or syria or syrian arab republic or tajikistan or tadjikistan or tadjhikistan or tadjhik or tanzania or tanganyika or thailand or siam or timor leste or east timor or togo or togolese republic or tonga or "trinidad and tobago" or trinidad or tobago or tunisia or turkey or turkmenistan or turkmen or uganda or ukraine or uruguay or uzbekistan or uzbek or vanuatu or new hebrides or venezuela or vietnam or viet nam or middle east or west bank or gaza or palestine or yemen or yugoslavia or zambia or zimbabwe or northern rhodesia or global south or africa south of the sahara or sub-saharan africa or subsaharan africa or africa, central or central africa or africa, northern or north africa or northern africa or magreb or maghrib or</p>	
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	<p>sahara or africa, southern or southern africa or africa, eastern or east africa or eastern africa or africa, western or west africa or western africa or west indies or indian ocean islands or caribbean or central america or latin america or "south and central america" or south america or asia, central or central asia or asia, northern or north asia or northern asia or asia, southeastern or southeastern asia or south eastern asia or southeast asia or south east asia or asia, western or western asia or europe, eastern or east europe or eastern europe or developing country or developing countries or developing nation? or developing population? or developing world or less developed countr* or less developed nation? or less developed population? or less developed world or lesser developed countr* or lesser developed nation? or lesser developed population? or lesser developed world or under developed countr* or under developed nation? or under developed population? or under developed world or underdeveloped countr* or underdeveloped nation? or underdeveloped population? or underdeveloped world or middle income countr* or middle income nation? or middle income population? or low income countr* or low income nation? or low income population? or lower income countr* or lower income nation? or lower income population? or underserved countr* or underserved nation? or underserved population? or underserved world or under served countr* or under served nation? or under served population? or under served world or deprived countr* or deprived nation? or deprived population? or deprived world or poor countr* or poor nation? or poor population? or poor world or poorer countr* or poorer nation? or poorer population? or poorer world or developing econom* or less developed econom* or lesser developed econom* or under developed econom* or underdeveloped econom* or middle income econom* or low income econom* or lower income econom* or low gdp or low gnp or low gross domestic or low gross national or lower gdp or lower gnp or lower gross domestic or lower gross national or lmic or lmic or third world or lami countr* or transitional countr* or emerging economies or emerging nation?).ti,ab,sh,kf.</p>	
54	52 and 53	1020

Scopus, Elsevier (79 records)

(((INDEXTERMS ("mobile application" OR "mobile phone" OR smartphone OR "text messaging") OR (TITLE-ABS (whatsapp OR telegram OR "Facebook Messenger" OR "Signal Private Messenger" OR "Signal app" OR bridgify OR kik OR snapchat OR skype OR keybase OR viber OR vibes OR threema OR siilo OR hospify OR simplepractice OR "Oncall health" OR trillian OR "Medic Bleep" OR wechat OR messengerpeople OR snapchat OR instagram OR twitter OR chatbot OR kakao OR wire OR tiger OR slack)) OR (TITLE-ABS (line PRE/3 (app OR apps OR application* OR platform))) OR (TITLE-ABS (("mobile health" OR mhealth OR m-health OR chat OR chatting OR messaging) PRE/0 (app OR apps OR application* OR platform* OR system* OR service* OR technolog* OR tool*))) OR (TITLE-ABS (informal PRE/0 ("mobile health" OR mhealth OR m-health))) OR (TITLE-ABS ((cellphone OR "cell phone" OR "cellular phone" OR mobile OR smartphone OR "smart phone") PRE/0 (app OR apps OR application* OR messaging OR messages))) OR (TITLE-ABS (("mobile phone" OR "mobile telephone") PRE/0 (app OR apps OR application*))) OR (TITLE-ABS ("text messaging" OR texting OR "text messages")) OR (TITLE-ABS ((mobile OR instant) PRE/0 messaging)) OR (TITLE-ABS (("short messaging" OR "short messages" OR "multimedia messaging" OR "multimedia messages") PRE/0 service*)) OR (TITLE-ABS ((sms OR mms OR communication) PRE/0 (app OR apps OR application*))) OR (TITLE-ABS ("messaging software"))) **AND** (INDEXTERMS ("qualitative research" OR interview) OR TITLE-ABS (qualitative OR interview* OR "thematic analysis" OR themes OR "mixed method" OR "mixed methods"))) **AND** (TITLE-ABS-KEY (afghanistan OR albania OR algeria OR "american samoa" OR angola OR "antigua and barbuda" OR antigua OR barbuda OR argentina OR armenia OR armenian OR aruba OR azerbaijan OR bahrain OR bangladesh OR barbados OR "republic of belarus" OR belarus OR byelarus OR belorussia OR byelorussian OR belize OR "british honduras" OR benin OR dahomey OR bhutan OR bolivia OR "bosnia and herzegovina" OR bosnia OR herzegovina OR botswana OR bechuanaland OR brazil OR brasil OR bulgaria OR "burkina faso" OR "burkina fasso" OR "upper volta" OR burundi OR urundi OR "cabo verde" OR "cape verde" OR cambodia OR kampuchea OR "khmer republic" OR cameroon OR cameron OR cameroun OR "central african republic" OR "ubangi shari" OR chad OR chile OR china OR colombia OR comoros OR "comoro islands" OR "iles comores" OR mayotte OR "democratic republic of the congo" OR "democratic republic congo" OR congo OR zaire OR "costa rica" OR "cote d'ivoire" OR "cote d ivoire" OR "cote divoire" OR "cote d ivoire" OR "ivory coast" OR croatia OR cuba OR cyprus OR "czech republic" OR czechoslovakia OR djibouti OR "french somaliland" OR dominica OR "dominican republic" OR ecuador OR egypt OR "united arab republic" OR "el salvador" OR "equatorial guinea" OR "spanish guinea" OR eritrea OR estonia OR eswatini OR swaziland OR ethiopia OR fiji OR gabon OR "gabonese republic" OR gambia OR "georgia (republic)" OR georgia OR georgian OR ghana OR "gold coast" OR gibraltar OR greece OR grenada OR guam OR guatemala OR guinea OR "guinea bissau" OR guyana OR "british guiana" OR haiti OR hispaniola OR honduras OR hungary OR india OR indonesia OR timor OR iran OR iraq OR "isle of man" OR jamaica OR jordan OR kazakhstan OR kazakh OR kenya OR "democratic people's republic of korea" OR "republic of korea" OR north AND korea OR south AND korea OR korea OR kosovo OR kyrgyzstan OR kirghizia OR kirgizstan OR "kyrgyz republic" OR kirghiz OR laos OR "lao pdr" OR "lao people's democratic republic" OR latvia OR lebanon OR "lebanese republic" OR lesotho OR basutoland OR liberia OR libya OR "libyan arab jamahiriya" OR lithuania OR macau OR macao OR "republic of north macedonia" OR macedonia OR madagascar OR "malagasy republic" OR malawi OR nyasaland OR malaysia OR "malay federation" OR "malaya federation" OR maldives OR "indian

ocean islands" OR "indian ocean" OR mali OR malta OR micronesia OR "federated states of micronesia" OR kiribati OR "marshall islands" OR nauru OR "northern mariana islands" OR palau OR tuvalu OR mauritania OR mauritius OR mexico OR moldova OR moldovian OR mongolia OR montenegro OR morocco OR ifni OR mozambique OR "portuguese east africa" OR myanmar OR burma OR namibia OR nepal OR "netherlands antilles" OR nicaragua OR niger OR nigeria OR oman OR muscat OR pakistan OR panama OR "papua new guinea" OR paraguay OR peru OR philippines OR philipines OR phillipines OR philippines OR poland OR "polish people's republic" OR portugal OR "portuguese republic" OR "puerto rico" OR romania OR russia OR "russian federation" OR ussr OR "soviet union" OR "union of soviet socialist republics" OR rwnda OR ruanda OR samoa OR "pacific islands" OR polynesia OR "samoan islands" OR "navigator island" OR "navigator islands" OR "sao tome and principe" OR "saudi arabia" OR senegal OR serbia OR seychelles OR "sierra leone" OR slovakia OR "slovak republic" OR slovenia OR melanesia OR "solomon island" OR "solomon islands" OR "norfolk island" OR "norfolk islands" OR somalia OR "south africa" OR "south sudan" OR "sri lanka" OR ceylon OR "saint kitts and nevis" OR "st. kitts and nevis" OR "saint lucia" OR "st. lucia" OR "saint vincent and the grenadines" OR "saint vincent" OR "st. vincent" OR grenadines OR sudan OR suriname OR surinam OR "dutch guiana" OR "netherlands guiana" OR syria OR "syrian arab republic" OR tajikistan OR tadjikistan OR tadhikistan OR tadhik OR tanzania OR tanganyika OR thailand OR siam OR "timor leste" OR "east timor" OR togo OR "togolese republic" OR tonga OR "trinidad and tobago" OR trinidad OR tobago OR tunisia OR turkey OR turkmenistan OR turkmen OR uganda OR ukraine OR uruguay OR uzbekistan OR uzbek OR vanuatu OR "new hebrides" OR venezuela OR vietnam OR "viet nam" OR "middle east" OR "west bank" OR gaza OR palestine OR yemen OR yugoslavia OR zambia OR zimbabwe OR "northern rhodesia" OR "global south" OR "africa south of the sahara" OR "sub saharan africa" OR "subsaharan africa" OR "africa, central" OR "central africa" OR "africa, northern" OR "north africa" OR "northern africa" OR magreb OR maghrib OR sahara OR "africa, southern" OR "southern africa" OR "africa, eastern" OR "east africa" OR "eastern africa" OR "africa, western" OR "west africa" OR "western africa" OR "west indies" OR "indian ocean islands" OR caribbean OR "central america" OR "latin america" OR "south and central america" OR "south america" OR "asia, central" OR "central asia" OR "asia, northern" OR "north asia" OR "northern asia" OR "asia, southeastern" OR "southeastern asia" OR "south eastern asia" OR "southeast asia" OR "south east asia" OR "asia, western" OR "western asia" OR "europe, eastern" OR "east europe" OR "eastern europe" OR "developing country" OR "developing countries" OR "developing nation" OR "developing nations" OR "developing population" OR "developing populations" OR "developing world" OR "less developed country" OR "less developed countries" OR "less developed nation" OR "less developed nations" OR "less developed population" OR "less developed populations" OR "less developed world" OR "lesser developed country" OR "lesser developed countries" OR "lesser developed nation" OR "lesser developed nations" OR "lesser developed population" OR "lesser developed populations" OR "lesser developed world" OR "under developed country" OR "under developed countries" OR "under developed nation" OR "under developed nations" OR "under developed population" OR "under developed populations" OR "under developed world" OR "underdeveloped country" OR "underdeveloped countries" OR "underdeveloped nation" OR "underdeveloped nations" OR "underdeveloped population" OR "underdeveloped populations" OR "underdeveloped world" OR "middle income country" OR "middle income countries" OR "middle income nation" OR "middle income nations" OR "middle income population" OR "middle income populations" OR "low income country" OR "low income countries" OR "low income nation" OR "low income nations" OR "low income population" OR "low income populations" OR "lower income country" OR "lower income countries" OR "lower income nation" OR "lower

income nations" OR "lower income population" OR "lower income populations" OR "underserved country" OR "underserved countries" OR "underserved nation" OR "underserved nations" OR "underserved population" OR "underserved populations" OR "underserved world" OR "underserved country" OR "underserved countries" OR "underserved nation" OR "underserved nations" OR "underserved population" OR "underserved populations" OR "underserved world" OR "deprived country" OR "deprived countries" OR "deprived nation" OR "deprived nations" OR "deprived population" OR "deprived populations" OR "deprived world" OR "poor country" OR "poor countries" OR "poor nation" OR "poor nations" OR "poor population" OR "poor populations" OR "poor world" OR "poorer country" OR "poorer countries" OR "poorer nation" OR "poorer nations" OR "poorer population" OR "poorer populations" OR "poorer world" OR "developing economy" OR "developing economies" OR "less developed economy" OR "less developed economies" OR "lesser developed economy" OR "lesser developed economies" OR "under developed economy" OR "under developed economies" OR "underdeveloped economy" OR "underdeveloped economies" OR "middle income economy" OR "middle income economies" OR "low income economy" OR "low income economies" OR "lower income economy" OR "lower income economies" OR "low gdp" OR "low gnp" OR "low gross domestic" OR "low gross national" OR "lower gdp" OR "lower gnp" OR "lower gross domestic" OR "lower gross national" OR "lami country" OR "lami countries" OR "transitional country" OR "transitional countries" OR "emerging economies" OR "emerging nation" OR "emerging nations"))